

MANAGEMENT OF VESTIBULAR SCHWANNOMAS: AGE MATTERS

¹Ergashev J.D., ²Santos S., ²Soto A., ¹Amonov Sh.E.

¹Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

²University clinic of Santiago de Compostela, Spain

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14030335>

Abstract. Vestibular schwannoma (VS) or Acoustic neuroma is a benign extra axial brain tumor arising from the lower portion of vestibular nerve. VS usually sporadic, but it may have a genetic origin known as Neurifibromatosis type 2. VS grow slowly with an average annual growth rate of 1.5 mm. Although, the VS considered a benign tumor, its growth may cause a serious problem to surrounding tissues. The aim of our study was to reveal and describe the age-related issues in the management of VS. In the framework of this research, 107 case reports of patients with a mean age of $57,0 \pm 14,50$ (R24-86) underwent thorough analysis. Patients with VS divided into 3 age groups: young adults 24-39, middle adults 47-59, and old adults $60 \leq$. Results of the study showed that selecting the proper treatment option for VS always correlated with tumor size and age of the patients. Young adults tend to have relatively rapid growing VS, and on the contrary, in old adults, the VS grow slowly. Thus, selection of a conservative approach in old adults prevents patients from unfavorable complications of traditional neurosurgery, and vice versa, traditional neurosurgery or radiosurgery may avoid young adults from adverse effects of VS growth.

Keywords: vestibular schwannoma, age-related approach, treatment, management.

Introduction. Vestibular schwannoma (VS) or acoustic neuroma is a benign extra axial brain tumor arising from the lower portion of vestibular nerve. VS usually sporadic, but it may have a genetic origin known as Neurifibromatosis type 2.

“De duro quodam corpusculo, nervio auditorio adherente” –were the first postmortem descriptions made for VS in 1777, by E. Sandiford who was a Professor of Pahology in Leiden (South Holland), in his book called “Anatome infantis cerebro destitute”. From 1777, the knowledge about VS has been accumulating more and more as well as the clinical symptoms in patients with VS which were correlated to the intracranial autopsy findings of many authors.

Until the 1900s the most physicians have been considering the intracranial surgery to be unwise and irresponsible. But in the early 1900s earlier tumour diagnosis and localization was possible and surgical intervention for intracranial pathology gained some popularity. Prominent surgeons such as von Monakow published optimistic papers encouraging doctors to be less reluctant in attempting intracranial surgery. As more surgeons independently attempted surgical intervention for VS, a variety of techniques and approaches developed, some of which were early versions of the procedures used today. Woolsey, Fraenkel, and Krause used a unilateral suboccipital approach with some success. Borchardt performed the first “transsigmoid” VS surgery in 1905 and the same year, Horsley first resected a VS.

As VS growth generates physical forces which compress important structures, like blood vessels, nerves and even brainstem. More VS cases have been diagnosed in last two decades because to improvements in imaging technology and more access to MRI.

Figure 1. Image shows the growth of a VS after one and a half years of observation (Source: Lassaletta L et al. An update on the treatment of vestibular schwannoma. *Acta Otorrinolaringol Esp.* 2009;60(2): pp131-140).

These are more common in the elderly population and are typically smaller in size [1].

In general, a benign-looking tumor by itself does not necessarily mean that it needs to be treated. Small VS that are recently diagnosed are frequently treated first with serial imaging and monitoring. Depending on a number of variables, such as the tumor's size at diagnosis, its notable growth on serial imaging, or the patient's symptoms, they are usually treated by either radiation therapy or surgical resection [1,3].

Tumor control has been transformed by the development of the Gamma Knife Machine for the treatment of VS patients. Professor Leksell performed the first Gamma Knife Surgery for VS in Sweden in 1969. The Leksell Gamma Knife type "B" was first made available in 1986. However, the results of GKS for VS were presented at the first international conference on VS in Copenhagen in 1991, which sparked a global interest in GKS. GKS was highlighted as the best course of action for elderly patients, patients who were at high risk for surgery, and patients who refused to have surgery. Numerous medical facilities have since reported positive GKS results for VS.

Aim of the study

The aim of our study was to reveal and describe the age-related issues in the management of VS.

Materials and methods of study

One hundred seven (107) patients with Vestibular Schwannoma (VS) underwent a retrospective study which has been implemented in the Galicia population which attended Santiago de Compostela University Hospital from the period between February 21, 1992 and May 05, 2011. Current study included only cases of VS and most of which were diagnosed by the means of gadolinium-enhanced MRI. As criteria of exclusion we have used the tumors apart from a VS or cases of CPA/IAC tumors of unknown origin.

Among the studied cases, there was 1 (0, 92%) young male, at the age of 36, who was diagnosed with a bilateral VS due to Neurofibromatosis Type II (NF2). In spite of knowing the clear distinct origin of the NF2, we have included this patient as a clinical presentation and the nature of the tumor was absolutely the same.

Methods of study included the results of gadolinium contrast MRI testing of brain and cerebellopontine angle (CPA), The Pure-tone Audiometry and other clinical data given in the patient's case reports/folder.

For statistical analysis we used Excel 2010 with further uploading the data to SPSS 20 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences).

Results

Among 107 (100.0%) patients, there were 57 (53.8%) females and 50 (46.2%) males, (e.g. see fig. 53) including 1 (0.9%) male patient with a bilateral VS due to NF2. Because of its genetic origin, we analyzed the bilateral VS separately and we will describe it at the end of the results.

Figure 2. Chart showing the distribution of patients by gender

Patients with VS divided into 3 age groups: young adults 24-39 years old, middle adults 47-59 years old, and old adults 60 or elders.

Among investigated unilateral VS patients there were 57 (53,8%) females with the median age of 57,45 ±14,24 (range, 24-86) and 49 (46, 2%) males with median age of 56,16 ±15,14 (range 24-85). Although the number of females was slightly higher than the number of males, but this difference was statistically not significant.

Gender	Number of cases & percentage	Age at the time of diagnosis		
		Median age/±	Age Range	IQR
Female	57 (53, 8%)	57,51 ±14,20	24-86	48-69,0
Male	49 (46, 2%)	56,21 ±14,97	24-86	43,5-69,5
Total	106 (100,0%)	57,0 ±14,50	24-86	46,7-69,0

Table 1. Distribution of VS patients by gender

In order to reveal the prevalence of hearing loss by age group and gender among the patients with a VS, we have conducted a comparative analysis between female and male patients. The mean values of a PTA in both groups do not differ significantly. Moreover, applied statistical tests (t-Student) did not show a statistically significant difference between two groups in terms of gender and hearing loss (p = 0.47).

The results of the analysis of MRI scan which determined the initial size of the VS in 106 (99.0%) patients was performed at the time of diagnosis. We have observed that the mean size of the tumor is a little bit bigger in the cases of males 17.37 (±9.05) than in the cases of females 14.96 (±10.16). Particularly, this difference was more pronounced in patients ≤ 40 years old (21.7 ±12.21 (6-50mm)) and this difference was negatively correlated in older patients. Although the tumor was

a determinant of size, statistical tests (t-Student) didn't show any significant difference in the size of the tumor between two genders.

In terms of age and the size of the tumor at the time of diagnosis we found a slight difference in males in presenting with relatively larger VS.

67 (63.2%) patients were under a wait-and-watch scan. Among them, there were 36 (53.2%) females and 31 (46.3%) males. The average age of patients in this group was 59.21 ± 14.35 (Range 24-85) and the average size of the VSs was 12.68 ± 6.76 (Range 2-35).

At the diagnostic stage, there were 27 (25.5%) patients directed to GK Radiosurgery. Among them there were 15 (55.67%) females and 12 (44.4%) males. The average age of patients in this group was 56.82 ± 14.30 (Range 24.75-78.48). In the group of patients under conventional neurosurgery, initially, there were 12 (11.32%) patients, including 6 (50.0%) females and 6 (50.0%) males. The average age of patients in this group was 43.78 ± 9.28 (Range 29.16 –57.85) years.

The stated results of three different groups slightly differ as patients in the conventional neurosurgery group are younger than the wait-and-watch and GK radiosurgery group $p=0.03$ (ANOVA). The average age of patients in radiosurgery and the wait-and-watch group shows no significant difference ($p = 0.19$) (t-Student). We do not find significant differences between genders in three treatment groups. The overall average PTA in the wait-and-watch and GK radiosurgery groups shows no significant difference.

Choosing the treatment option for VS continues to be a challenging issue for more than 100 years because of their benign nature and potentially significant surgical morbidity and mortality related to the complex anatomy of the CPA. However, in recent years, development of new diagnostic modalities such as the CT, the MRI and the auditory evoked potentials has resulted in the drastic decrease in the average size of a VS at diagnosis.

Using the serial MRI also enables the control of non-growing VSs, thereby warning of possible complications of Conventional Neurosurgery and/or Radiosurgery.

	Factors influencing to selection of treatment modality	Treatment modalities		
		Wait-and-watch	Radiosurgery	Neurosurgery
Tumor size	$\geq 20\text{mm}$		+	++
	10-15	+	+	
	≤ 10	++	+	
Age	≥ 60	+	+	+
	45-60	+	++	+
	≤ 45	+	+	+
Tumor localization	Intracanal	+	++	+
	Extracanal	++	++	+++
	Intra-Extracanal	+	++	++
PTA$\geq 50\text{dB}$	Yes	++	+	
	No	+	++	+

Table 2. The plus signs show factors which influence of VS treatment options

There are also some other important factors which may influence the decision of either treatment options and one of those factors could be the clinical presentation. Although the

predictive value was limited, the symptoms of vertigo, facial paralysis and hearing loss may be the indicators which predict tumor growth.

Conclusion

Selecting the proper treatment option for VS always correlated with tumor size and age of the patients. Young adults tend to have relatively rapid growing VS, and on the contrary, in old adults, the VS grow slowly. Thus, selection of a conservative approach in old adults prevents patients from unfavorable complications of traditional neurosurgery, and vice versa, traditional neurosurgery or radiosurgery may avoid young adults from adverse effects of VS growth. In case of patients with small tumors, wait-and-watch and GK Radiosurgery are effective in controlling the growth of the vestibular schwannomas. For old adults with a small vestibular schwannoma, the wait-and-watch protocol is a correct therapeutic approach which does not worsen the medium-term prognosis.

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